

ETHNOLOGY

CONCEPTELE DE IDENTITATE ȘI SĂRBĂTORI, RAPORTATE LA DIASPORA ROMÂNEASCĂ

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IDENTITY AND FESTIVE PRACTICES CONNECTED TO THE ROMANIAN DIASPORA

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Rezumat

Lucrarea de față face parte dintr-un studiu mai amplu, ce își propune să analizeze conceptele de identitate și sărbătoare, în raport cu diaspora românească, în contextul globalizării și al migrației. Multiculturalismul și interculturalitatea sunt evidente; de aceea o analiză a conceptului de *identitate*, ca aspect relevant al vieții sociale, culturale și cotidiene, este imperios necesară. Consider acest lucru deoarece asistăm la apariția unor comunități minoritare, etnice, cunoscute sub termenul generic de *diaspora*; care se raportează într-un mod special la identitate, pendulând permanent între două culturi (cea din țara natală și cea din țara de adopție). Există diverse forme de identitate: culturală, națională, istorică, publică, etnică, de opțiune, pozitivă/negativă, socială, profesională. Una dintre identitățile la care ne vom referi este *identitatea socială*, ce presupune apartenența individului la un anumit grup social și conștientizarea acestui aspect. O altă formă definitorie pentru orice om este *identitatea națională*, în construirea căreia un rol important îi revine memoriei sociale. Fiecare popor, un anumit grup social sau comunitar își revendică propria identitate, un rol definitoriu avându-l limba maternă, raportarea la cult, dar și la tradiție, la valori. Ia naștere, în acest mod, *identitatea culturală*, cel mai important aspect al acesteia fiind limbajul, comunicarea. Un alt tip de identitate, ce are legătură directă cu migrația, este *identitatea de opțiune*; la care se adaugă o *identitate revendicativă*, specifică românilor emigranți apatrizi, *exilații*, *pribegii* de dinainte de Revoluția din 1989, contestatarii condițiilor de trai din propria țară. Deși fiecare resimte diferit ruperea de țară, cu toții experimentează *condiția străinului*.

Lucrarea ilustrează și noțiunea de *sărbătoare*, prezentând calendarul obiceiurilor și sărbătorilor românești – reminiscențe în unele comunități românești din diaspora. Opțiunea de a le studia este motivată de bogăția folclorului pe care românii l-au dus peste granițele țării, *l-au exportat*. Acestea, cuprinse în sărbătorile noastre, sunt asemenea unor verigi dintr-un lanț în care se îmbină armonios datini, obiceiuri, practici, ritualuri, credințe, în care se explică reciproc spiritul și materia. Ele au un *caracter unitar*, în ciuda micilor diferențe care apar, în funcție de regiunile țării din care au plecat românii aflați în diaspora. Sărbătorile tradiționale sunt mereu vii, chiar dacă unele dintre tradițiile aferente lor nu se conservă, ci se transformă: unele parțial, altele radical sau sunt compuse, după vechile scheme, și reinvestite cu funcții sau simboluri noi.

În concluzie, elementul popular stă la originea fiecărui popor în parte, îl definește ființial și identitar și tocmai de aceea, atunci când ne îndreptăm spre alte zări, el nu poate fi lăsat deoparte pentru că este adânc înrădăcinat în ființa românului, oriunde s-ar afla.

Abstract

This article is part of a broader study that aims to analyze the concepts of *identity* and *celebration* in relation to the Romanian diaspora, in the context of globalization and migration. Multiculturalism and interculturality make it evident that analyzing the concept of identity as a relevant aspect of social, cultural, and daily life is important. This necessity stems from the emergence of minority ethnic communities, commonly known as *diasporas*, which relate to identity in a particular way, constantly oscillating between two cultures: that of the country of origin and that of the host country. There are various forms of identity: cultural, national, historical, public, ethnic, elective, positive/negative, social, and professional. One of the identities addressed in this study is *social identity*, which involves an individual's belonging to a particular social group and awareness of that belonging. Another defining form for any individual is *national identity*, in the construction of which social memory plays an important role. Each person, as well as any social or community group, claims its own identity, the mother tongue, religious affiliation, tradition, and values playing a determining role. Language, or communication, is the primary factor in establishing *cultural identity*. Another type of identity directly related to migration is the *identity of choice*, complemented by a *revealing identity* specific to emigrants, Romanian exiles, and stateless displaced persons who were challenged by living conditions in their country of origin before the 1989 Revolution. Although each experiences the separation from their homeland differently, all share the *condition of strangeness*.

The article also illustrates the concept of *celebration* by presenting the calendar of Romanian customs and festivals as preserved in some communities of the Romanian diaspora. The decision to study these traditions is

motivated by the richness of folklore that Romanians have brought beyond the borders of the country. These elements, embodied in the Romanian celebrations, resemble links in a chain where customs, practices, rituals, and beliefs intertwine harmoniously, explaining each other's spirit and matter. They present a unitary character, despite minor differences that manifest themselves depending on the regions from which the Romanians of the diaspora come. Traditional festivals remain alive even if some of their associated customs are not preserved but transformed: some partially, others radically, or reconfigured according to older patterns and reinvested with new functions or symbols.

In conclusion, the folk element lies at the origin of every people, defining them existentially and identically. For this reason, when individuals move to other horizons, it cannot be left behind, because it is deeply rooted in Romanian being, wherever they are.

Cuvinte-cheie: identitate, sărbători, tradiții, diaspora, limba maternă.

Keywords: identity, festivals, traditions, diaspora, mother tongue.

In a modern world, characterized by diversity, promoting a society that tends toward globalization, in which multiculturalism and trans culturalism increasingly become commonplace, an analysis of the concept of *identity*, as a relevant aspect of social, cultural, and everyday life, becomes imperative. Globalization, which has generated extensive migratory movements, has led to the emergence of minority ethnic communities, generically known as *diasporas*, which relate to identity in a particular way, constantly oscillating between two cultures: that of the country of origin and that of the host country. It is generally accepted that identity exists in multiple forms: cultural, national, historical, public, ethnic, identity by choice, positive or negative identity, social identity, professional identity, and others. "The notion of *identity* is polysemic; it appears both in everyday language and in the vocabulary of psychology, psychoanalysis, and philosophy." [1] The present study proposes a minimal definition of several of these concepts, which serve the purpose of this work and will be developed further as required. One of the identities addressed here is *social identity*, defined as "the individual's awareness of belonging to a particular social group, together with the emotional and evaluative significance attached to that membership." [2] From this definition arise three essential coordinates: "individuals recognize that they belong to a specific group, experience this belonging emotionally, and assign value to their membership in that group." [3]

The authors of one of the foundational theories of social identity, Henri Tajfel and John C. Turner [4], argued that individuals generally seek a positive self-conception in order to maintain or increase self-esteem. However, certain social groups or categories to which one belongs may carry either positive or negative connotations, generating correspondingly positive or negative social identities. In this way, social groups contribute decisively to shaping an individual's social identity. When one's own group is evaluated in comparison with another group, through the comparison of attributes or values, a positive or negative difference may emerge. In the case of Romanians living beyond the country's borders, or those intending to emigrate, such a difference often appears as negative, associated with diminished prestige. Consequently, social identity becomes unsatisfactory, and individuals attempt to leave their group of origin, hoping to gain access elsewhere to a more positively valued group. Upon arrival in the host country, *as emigrants or foreigners*, they frequently encounter the same condition of negative social identity and "begin to act in ways intended to improve the status

of their own group." [5] A situation of this kind is described by Gina Stoiciu in her book *Acasă. Cei plecați în lume*, where she reflects on the experience of Romanian emigrants in Montreal, Canada, beginning in the 1980. [6]

Another defining form of identity for any individual is *national identity*, in whose construction social memory plays a decisive role: "the notion of identity depends on memory and vice versa... Identity, that *hard core* of personality, is sustained by the recollection of how we related in the past to other people, to society, and to values." [7] We assume a particular identity based on what we consciously remember; voluntary recollections of the past shape the representations we hold about ourselves in the present. Every person, or even a particular social or community group, claims its own identity, perceived as *something sacred*. [8] If personal identity represents a set of qualities and flaws belonging to the same individual, and social identity refers to the specificity of a group in terms of gender, profession, religion, or social status, national identity occupies a different plane. As Chelcea argues, "national identity, like ethnic identity, constitutes a *fundamental identity group*: from the first days of life, the newborn begins reacting to stimuli from the surrounding world, especially to the presence of the mother, who herself belongs to a nationality, speaks a language, and follows a system of values, including religious ones. In acquiring the mother tongue, the candidate for humanity becomes fully human." [9]

In this way, *cultural identity* emerges, with language and communication as its central components. The importance of the mother tongue for national identity is therefore crucial, since "the mother tongue determines our human identity and nourishes our inner being." [10] From this perspective, another essential dimension of national identity, despite the coexistence with other religious denominations, remains Orthodox, particularly visible in Romanian diaspora communities. There, the church, and especially the Orthodox Church, plays a crucial role in preserving and affirming national identity. Thus, "both the mother tongue and religious affiliation may function as *poles around which national identity crystallizes*." [11] From these derive, implicitly, the collective self-awareness of a nation or ethnic group.

Modern societies also *invent traditions*, and many historians argue that such practices attempt to establish continuity with the historical past. There is, however, a risk inherent in the invention of traditions when they

imply a rupture from older practices. Invented traditions are often accompanied by *invented celebrations*, some belonging to contemporary or urban folklore. While *older traditions* are generally tied to ritual practices, social customs, and even superstitions, *invented* ones differ in form but frequently promote similar moral values, such as patriotism, loyalty, and duty. Among invented celebrations are those that mobilize the Romanian tricolor and national emblem, reflecting the *political symbolism* present in every nation. Within Romanian families abroad, in community associations, churches, or sporting events involving Romanian representatives, the national flag is almost always present. Such practices have generated celebrations such as *National Flag Day* (26 June), *Romanian Language Day* (31 August), *Romanian Culture Day*, *The Day of Romanians Everywhere* (25 May), *International Family Day*, *Grandparents' Day*, *United Nations Day*, and many others carrying symbolic meaning.

Returning to the concept of identity, we may mention a category directly linked to migration, namely *identity by choice*. Some researchers argue that, for any nation, history and the territory of the homeland become *objects of symbolic reverence*. The individual becomes fully human by assuming, throughout the process of socialization, the origin and history of the group into which they are born and within which they live. The past, recalled in memory, represents a durable source of identity and *a program for the present*. [12] When an individual, a group, or an entire population leaves its native territory and severs this connection," it loses the identity prescribed by birth and adopts an *identity by choice*." [13] This situation is particularly relevant in the case of Romanian emigrants, especially the stateless, the *exiles*, and the *wanderers* before the 1989 Revolution. They fall into the category of individuals with a *vindictive identity* [14] generated by their opposition to the living conditions in their homeland. Most contested political power discreetly and tacitly, out of fear of repression, constructing in this way a *negative identity* that extended to a large part of Romanian society. The more courageous among them chose to leave the country in the hope of building a positive identity elsewhere. Many, however, encountered unexpected barriers, the most immediate and painful being the language barrier. These experiences are reflected in numerous accounts from members of the diaspora. Although each person experiences separation from the homeland differently, all confront the *condition of the foreigner*, which may appear as a form of dispossession of identity produced by *uprooting*. [15] For each individual, departure represents a unique experience. It is often perceived as an act of courage, an adventure of one's own life, a destiny consciously shaped and assumed, yet nostalgia and, frequently, loneliness inevitably make themselves felt. "Estrangement, initially experienced as isolation, gradually becomes an attentive observation of an unfamiliar world and a lucid observation of life itself. The paradox of choice is that one can never know whether the chosen path was the right one." [16] In order to understand this experience, the emigrant turns to memory, because *the first life becomes the past*. Chronological order is one thing, voluntary

memory another; memory builds bridges within a multicultural world, since "identity and memory are not things we think about, but things with which we think." [17]

Within this context of preserving identity, Romanian folklore assumes an essential role, especially the calendar of customs and celebrations and their remnants within diaspora communities. The motivation to study the persistence of Romanian traditions abroad arises from the richness of folklore that Romanians took it across the country's borders, *exported it*, a term used by Flaviu Predescu, within the show *Romanian traditions in the Diaspora*. [18] The popular element stands at the origin of every people; it defines them both ontologically and in terms of identity, remaining inseparable from them regardless of where they move. As Cocchiara argues, "the discovery of the primitive and popular element is not an external act, but a given of our consciousness that provides new and original experiences." [19]

A history of peoples, and particularly of the Romanian people, necessarily includes a history of folklore, which constitutes an integral part of the history of civilization and culture. Folklore is a complex ensemble that incorporates customs, traditions, rituals, beliefs, and superstitions, a vast spectrum of popular life manifestations existing within civilizations. It represents the intersection of several disciplines, including philology, anthropology, ethnography, sociology, and psychology. Its unity derives from the heritage preserved, affirmed, promoted, and often recreated by each people. The concept of *people* itself refers to "A well-defined particularity that responds to certain ethical or spiritual interests towards which one's own actions and thoughts aim [...] is the expression of a certain vision of life, of some certain spiritual attitudes, of thought, of culture, of customs, of a civilization that presents itself with its own characteristics, specific, well structured. This is the very nature of folklore [...] The folk is always as history has created it: a history not only political, but a historical life in all its manifestations, from language to economy, from law to morals." [20]

The folk is first composed of individuals who pass through successive stages of life marked by key human moments: birth, marriage, and death. These transitions often involve shifts in social status or even movement between societies, and each transformation generates both profane and sacred reactions. Life events, past and present, define the human being, society, and its relationship with nature and the universe, all subject to ritual frameworks. *Tradition* crowns these processes, rooted deeply in the past yet constantly reflected in the present, and this is the domain studied by folklore. The promotion of Romanian traditions is also motivated by the desire to awaken national consciousness among Romanians wherever they may live. Preserving and transmitting these traditions safeguards not only ways of life but also forms of authentic Romanian artistic expression. They create bridges between people, between past and future, and between generations. "It cannot be denied that the study of folklore has always contributed to overcoming the spiritual and cultural boundaries of each people to reach towards the end the recognition of a wider community, the one that unites people with

each other. The generous competition [...] eager to save everything that each person and each nation has most intimate starts, of course, from a national feeling [...] The very concept of Europe, the new concept of Europe, remains useless and empty, if it is not decisively introduced into the circle of those cultural and moral factors to whose creation it contributed folklore. Because folklore urged researchers to think in English, in German, in Russian, and in other languages, but at the same time urged them to think in European, according to an expression of Mrs. Stäel." [21]

This dynamic becomes evident when examining Romanian traditions carried beyond national borders. These traditions, embedded in celebrations, function as links in a chain where customs, practices, rituals, and beliefs intertwine harmoniously, mutually explaining the relationship between spirit and matter. They survive precisely because they respond to deeply rooted emotional structures within Romanian identity. The connection between Romanians and their homeland persists even among those who left in anger or disappointment. The bond remains internal, because "Transplanting traditions outside their native soil resembles inviting guests into a household after changing their clothes, while their essence remains intact." [22] It can be noted, at the same time, that the *unitary character* of the traditions and customs of our people, despite the small differences that appear depending on the regions of the country from which the Romanian diaspora left: "The people have their songs and their customs, their stories, and their holidays [...] like the leaves of a tree that sinks its roots into the past, from where it draws the sap of the future." [23]

Anything that originates from the people and returns to them in forms they preserve and value may be considered *popular*, and celebrations belong to this sphere. *Popular traditions stand at the foundation of human existence.* [24] Traditional celebrations remain alive even when some associated practices are transformed or forgotten; common ritual forms continue to appear at crucial moments in human life, wherever *their bearers* migrate. Some traditions change partially, others radically, and some are recomposed according to older patterns and reinvested with new meanings or functions.

The Romanian ethnographer Simion Florea Marian presents, in his monumental ethnographic study *Romanian Celebrations* (original title: *Sărbătorile la români*), a detailed portrait of the popular calendar. Divided into three volumes, the work is grounded in extensive documentation and focuses on *what Romanians themselves believe and say about their celebrations.* [25] Marian acknowledges that certain customs disappear while others replace them, yet insists that their study remains necessary for ethnographers, anthropologists, and historians alike. His monographic research includes both church celebrations and those considered pagan or unrelated to official religious practice but still respected by the people. Although many ancient celebrations have faded over time, certain rituals and beliefs have survived in adapted forms. "The celebrations to which Marian devotes the greatest attention are those that continue to hold strong resonance within Romanian communities worldwide, regardless of geographic

location. Among the most significant within his study are the New Year and Easter cycles, which occupy the largest ritual and symbolic space." [26]

Both in the conception of the ethnographer S. Fl. Marian, and in that of the Romanian people, the Christian holiday of Holy Easter is considered "the greatest, most important, most sacred and joyful holiday of the year." [27] It is known that it is a holiday celebrated in spring and this thing is not accidental at all because nature is also revived with Christ and with the triumph over death which the Savior brings. What draws attention in this study and is related to our approach regarding the reminiscences of traditional Romanian holidays in the diaspora, is that distinct note that is found in all chapters dedicated to major holidays, regarding the detailed presentation of manifestations that we find on the day of a certain holiday, which have continued until the days of our time, including in Romanian communities outside the country's borders. Some precede major holidays, others are held on the very day of the holiday, and others follow it. For example, in Holy Week, which precedes the great feast of the Resurrection of the Lord, people engage in household chores already established, such as: the so-called spring cleaning, which must be done at any cost before (the same thing happens on the occasion of Christmas and New Year, especially since the threshold of houses and churches will be trod by the heralds of the Nativity of the Lord: carolers, the Star, the Herod or *Viflaim*, the *Goat*, the *Buhai*); to which are added rituals indispensable for any housewife who respects herself, including: beautifying the house, baking the Easter bread, called *pasca*, painting the eggs and preparing the lamb. Some foods, considered ritual foods (for example: round or elongated cakes, those called old men or old women, pies, prosphora or the notorious Easter lamb) generate a true spirit of competition, which has been maintained among the diaspora, taking care to present and offer them for tasting to *foreigners* from the country of adoption, in the midst of which they live. Some of these have become small entrepreneurs and have even developed businesses that thrive around the holidays traditional consecrated, especially (the well-known Romanian stores that have appeared all over the world, especially where large communities of Romanians live); others prefer to procure from their homeland, directly from producers or from family members, as ingredients as natural as possible, which can bring to the holiday table the specific taste and smell of the holidays at home. A special place is occupied by egg painting (a ritual about which we find multiple meanings and explanations in the mentioned trilogy earlier).

It is worth noting that S. Fl. Marian, spreads beyond the Romanian space, making references to other ethnographic areas as well. Thus, he mentions that "the tradition of red eggs was also held by other peoples: Romans, Persians, Greeks, Gauls, Egyptians, Italians, Spaniards, as well as peoples from South America." [28] The erudite ethnographer also paid special attention to the legends about painted eggs, highlighting, thus, the folk art put in the service of respecting such customs; detailing aspects related to the color range used for *painting eggs*. Moreover, he also gave a speech at the Romanian Academy, a reception speech on the

popular chromatic theme. Egg painting in a traditional, but also with methods that are more and more modern, remains a defining element for the feast of Holy Easter, in all Romanian communities around the globe, and the custom of inviting folk craftsmen skilled in the realization of this technique has already become a tradition, which the Romanians from diaspora presents with pride to the general public, invited to the various events occasioned by of this great Christian holiday. The feeling of national pride corresponds, however, from the most distant times, also this feeling of *Christian brotherhood* [29] that Romanians prove not only to their fellow countrymen, but also to all their fellow human beings, regardless of religion or nationality. What is notable to remember from the celebration of holidays is the way in which the Romanian has valued time, but also the way in which he combined what is sacred with what is profane, because this eminently religious holiday is accompanied by so many customs of not only a festive, but also a profane nature. S. Fl. Marian's trilogy "proposed, for the first time in our specialized literature, not only a conclusive image of a part of the Romanians' holidays, seen as a coherent whole, but also a definition of them..." [30]

The scholarly successor of S. FL. Marian (because he could not finalize the project of including, in their entirety, the holidays of the year) is Tudor Pamfile, who divided the holidays among Romanians into depending on the seasons, as follows: Summer holidays, among which are some that are preserved, are respected and celebrated by Romanians beyond the country's borders, some even being invested with new functions and symbols: Summer *Moşii* (memorial service), Pentecost Celebration, *Sânzienele*, Holy Apostles Peter and Paul, St. Ilie; Autumn holidays and Christmas Fast: Saint Mary – The Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary and The Birth of the Blessed Virgin Mary, Day of the Cross, Autumn All Souls' Day, Holy Archangels Michael and Gabriel, St. Andrew, St. Nicolae, *Ignatul* (pig slaughter). Separately, he treats Christmas, enumerating "the customs and beliefs that together make up the Christmas holiday." [31] Both days are regarded as significant, the traditions related to this period, elements of the specific ritual, customs, habits of this holiday cherished, among which: waiting for the holidays, cakes and sweet bread, father Christmas, the blessing the Christmas Eve table, caroling, Star o'caroling, *Viflein* or *Irozii*; the Goat (the Turk), *Brezaia*; slaughtering the pigs; Christmas, autumn All Souls' Day, the Christmas Tree, and others. About the legendary person of Christmas speaks in Chapter VIII, mentioning in one of the two final chapters: "Christmas is the man who drove the mother of God out of his house in the hour of birth, but later, after birth repented and gave glory to God. This is what the legends tell us, which in their wide garb of prose can keep it clearer, something that cannot be asked of a carol, often out of the pen of a scholar [...]. Christmas includes many customs, like Easter." [32]

Today it is quite difficult to assess how much of what is specifically Romanian, autochthonous, and authentic can still be found in the culture of the people. Despite the course of human evolution and the fact that Romanians have come to spread across the world and engage with an increasingly evident multiculturalism,

the capacity of folkloric models to capture diverse social realities and to express them in varied forms persists. This endurance is due to the fact that each generation, in one way or another, inherits and carries forward the traditions of its people, particularly those centered on the major festivals of the annual cycle. No culture of a people exists alone, but coexists with other cultures, especially in this century in which borders are open and free movement is no longer just a beautiful dream; Romanian culture is not outside of that European, nor that of the universal, because artistic values circulate *in both directions*. [33] Based on these considerations, Constantin Eretescu compiles a classification of all aspects related to folk literature as a source of inspiration for written literature, gathering factual and classifying folklore, which is, at least in Romania, a syncretic phenomenon.

I consider this aspect important because it can serve as a starting point for comparative and conclusive research on how many of these traditions have evolved within Romanian diaspora communities, and which have disappeared, either through neglect or as a result of reinterpretation. Certainly, we can speak of a permanent recreation of them and not of a disappearance, with some exceptions. Moreover, referring to this aspect, namely the existence of an unquestionable connection between people, the ethnologist, anthropologist, and writer Constantin Eretescu remarked that: "The literary folklore of Romanians was formed in the context of their coexistence with other peoples. Differences in language have never hindered the migration of cultural values." [34]

We find that the folklore of customs is mostly preserved in modern society today and in Romanian communities everywhere, which is visible in the holidays throughout the year or in the crucial moments of human existence, wherever they may be, being updated in a sacred time. The ritual act is indispensable in the folklore of customs, and it reveals its syncretic character because, surprisingly or not, even today, in all corners of the world where Romanians live, certain ancient rituals are practiced, even if they are most often disguised under a new guise. Rituals differ not only from one historical era to another but also from the point of view of the meaning, functions they fulfill, or their motivation. The mentality of those who practice them has determined transformations of these, but these metamorphoses somehow confirm their perennity: "The contemporary form of unfolding of some customs is, therefore, the complex result of the successive modifications to which they have been subjected." [35]

On a similar note, trying to synthesize folklore to relate it to the latest realities, which are still preserved and received by folklorists, Romanian holiday calendars provide an admirable synthesis of the country's beliefs, customs, and traditions, key markers of national identity examined in depth in Professor Antoaneta Olteanu's monumental work, *Space and Time in Romanian Traditions*. We find here: Calendar of holidays with a fixed date, Calendar of mobile holidays, Calendar of seasons, Weekly calendar, Calendar of days and nights, and Lunar calendar. This work has relevance for our research because it includes a vast ethnological material, through which we are offered an updated version

of all the holidays that we can find in the Romanian villages and, from here, carried to other horizons by our Romanians, more or less tributary to them, who have spread around the world and taken with them part of the wealth and beauty of Romanian folklore, many of them trying to create a piece of Romania where they are. The author offers " [...] a gradual presentation of the festive. In addition to traditions and customs, which synthetically provide the data best known, best preserved of the holiday, numerous magical practices are offered, which emphasize the active participation of people in the sacredness of the day." [36]

Thus, in the calendar of holidays with a fixed date, we find the winter holidays (starting with St. Andrew the Apostle's Day – which has been decreed in recent years as the Patron Saint of Romania, St. Nicholas, Christmas, New Year, Epiphany, and Saint John), with all the related traditions, are described in detail some of them exported and practiced beyond the country's borders, with Romanian carols holding a place of honor, without exception, and in some areas even *Viflainm* or *Irozii*, *Plugușorul*, *Capra* (or *Turca*), *Sorcova*; practiced in some diaspora communities or presented not only to Romanians, but also to the general public from the countries of adoption, through countless shows, festivals or parades initiated by generous people, the Church, various Associations, with the support of the Department for Romanians from Everywhere, the Embassies or other political or apolitical bodies and organizations, NGOs, etc.

All these represent *a unique form of art*, which we, as Romanians, have a duty to preserve, to promote and cultivate it further in the souls of the younger generations, especially among those born abroad, international children, who *evolve in a present without memories and without a past*. [37]

The aspects presented in this article constitute a first step in a broader study, which aims to highlight Romanian customs, habits, and traditions, in which there are values authentic to the Romanian people.

References

1. Gadrey, Nicole (1995), as cited in Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 9.
2. Tajfel, Henri (1972), as cited in Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 11.
3. Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 11.
4. Tajfel, Henri (1979) & Turner, John, C. (1982), as cited in Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 11.
5. Doise, W., Deschamps, J.C. & Mugny, G. (1996), as cited in Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 13.
6. Stoiciu, Gina. *Home in the world*, ProUniversitaria Publishing House, 2022.
- 7., 8. Gills, J.R. (1994), as cited in, Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 14.
9. Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 15.
10. Gerardus, Lens, Nicolas (1993), as cited in, Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 15.
11. Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 16.
12. Schwarz, B. (1996), as cited in, Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p.16.
- 13., 14. Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, pp. 17 - 18.
- 15., 16. Stoiciu, Gina. *Home in the world*, ProUniversitaria Publishing House, 2022, p. 26.
17. Gills, J.R. (1994), as cited in Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, 1998, p. 19.
18. Predescu, Flaviu. *Debate Romanian Traditions in the Diaspora*, Edition I, June 28 2024, starting at 13:00 (Romanian local time). Show produced by DCNEWS, Project financed by the Department for Romanians Everywhere, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WuvIK05WeaQ> (accessed on 31.05.2025, at 13.36).
- 19., 20. Cocchiara, Giuseppe. *History of European folklore studies. Europe in search of itself*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, 2004, pp. 8 - 11.
21. Cocchiara, Giuseppe. *History of European folklore studies. Europe in search of itself*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, 2004, pp. 217–218.
- 22., 23. Cocchiara, Giuseppe. *History of European folklore studies. Europe in search of itself*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, 2004, p. 283.
24. Cocchiara, Giuseppe. *History of European folklore studies. Europe in search of itself*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, 2004, p. 132.
- 25., 26., 27., 28., 29., 30. Marian, S. Fl. *Holidays in Romania*, Polisalm Publishing House, 2022, pp. 10 - 17.
- 31., 32. Pamfile, Tudor. *Holidays in Romania*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, 2018, p. 399.
- 33., 34. Eretescu, Constantin. *Literary folklore of Romanians. A contemporary look*, Spandugino Publishing House, 2022, p. 14.
35. Eretescu, Constantin. *Literary folklore of Romanians. A contemporary look*, Spandugino Publishing House, 2022, p. 28.
36. Olteanu, Antoaneta. *Space and time in Romanian traditions*, Publishing House Paideia, 2018, p. 353.
37. Stoiciu, Gina. *Home in the world*, ProUniversitaria Publishing House, 2022, p. 169.
38. Chelcea, Septimiu. *Social memory and national identity*. Publishing House National Information Institute/ I.N.I, Bucharest, 1998.

39. Cocchiara, Giuseppe. *History of European folklore studies. Europe in search of itself*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, Bucharest, 2004.
40. Eretescu, Constantin. *Literary folklore of Romanians. A contemporary look*, Spandugino Publishing House, Bucharest, 2022.
41. Marian, S. Fl. *Holidays in Romania*, Polisalm Publishing House, Chişinău, 2022.
42. Olteanu, Antoaneta. *Space and time in Romanian traditions*, Publishing House Paideia, Bucharest, 2018.
43. Pamfile, Tudor. *Holidays in Romania*, SAECULUM I.O. Publishing House, Bucharest, 2018.
44. Predescu, Flaviu. *Debate Romanian Traditions in the Diaspora*, Edition I, June 28, 2024, starting at 13:00 (Romanian local time). Show produced by DCNEWS, Project financed by the Department for Romanians Everywhere, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WuvIK05WeaQ> (accessed on 31.05.2025, at 13.36).
45. Stoiciu, Gina. *Home in the world*, ProUniversitaria Publishing House, Bucharest, 2022.